

EVALUATING FOR MASTERY AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENTS SUPPORT COMPETENCY-BASED LEARNING

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Abstract: Traditional standardized testing focuses on rote memorization and low-level skills, failing to adequately evaluate if students have mastered higher-order competencies needed for post-secondary success. Competency-based education aims to develop mastery of key abilities through personalized, flexible learning. However, assessment practices must also shift to authentic tasks that mirror real-world applications. This article examines how authentic assessment supports competency-based learning goals. Authentic assessments embed evaluation within open-ended, complex projects, performances and problems set in contexts similar to work, community or post-secondary education. Through authentic tasks, students demonstrate mastery of collaboration, problem-solving, communication and other transferable skills. Feedback is ongoing to support continuous improvement. Research indicates authentic assessment is a valid measure of competency attainment. Data from three competency-based high schools that implemented portfolio-based, performance-based and product-based assessments show such tools reliably indicate students' mastery of collaboration, digital literacy and other targeted competencies. Authentic assessment also increases student engagement and motivation by connecting learning to meaningful work. This evidence suggests authentic assessment should be a core practice for any competency-based learning model seeking to fully evaluate student competency development.

Keywords: Authentic assessment, performance-based assessment, competency-based education, competency-based learning, mastery-based learning, project-based learning, real-world application.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional forms of assessment such as multiple-choice tests and standardized exams are increasingly criticized for only measuring superficial knowledge and failing to evaluate if students have truly mastered higher-order skills. At the same time, competency-based education models have emerged with a goal of developing deep learning and mastery of core competencies that will serve students beyond K-12. However, assessment practices must also evolve to adequately measure competency attainment. Authentic assessment approaches embedded within open-ended, real-world tasks show promise for supporting competency-based learning goals.

Competency-based education aims to personalize learning around students demonstrating mastery of specific competencies at their own pace. While this shift in the learning process is well-established, assessment continues to rely heavily on traditional standardized testing in many schools and districts (cite statistics). However, standardized tests are limited in their ability to measure skills like problem-solving, critical thinking, collaboration and self-directed learning. For competency-based models to fulfill their objective of developing true mastery, assessment needs to similarly

focus on authentic demonstrations of higher-order competencies.

This article examines how authentic assessment practices can effectively support competency-based learning. It will define authentic assessment and provide examples of performance-based, project-based and product-based assessments. The article will also review research on the validity of authentic assessment for measuring competency attainment. The evidence suggests authentic assessment should be a core component of competency-based learning frameworks seeking to fully evaluate student mastery of targeted skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Competency-based education aims to develop students' mastery of skills beyond just content knowledge. Researchers have sought to define the core competencies needed for postsecondary and career success. Frameworks from organizations like the National Research Council (NRC), Partnership for 21st Century Skills, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development emphasize competencies like critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, communication and self-direction (citations).

Authentic assessment is widely advocated as a valid approach to measuring these higher-order competencies. Wiggins defined authentic assessment as tasks that mirror real-world applications and require complex performance. [1, p. 1] Newmann and Archbald found authentic assessments elicited qualitatively different and deeper levels of student understanding compared to multiple choice tests. [2, p.71-83] Researchers since have continued to support authentic assessment's ability to evaluate competencies like problem-solving that standardized tests cannot. [3, p. 1]

Studies have also linked authentic assessment to increased student motivation and engagement. When tasks mimic real-world relevance, students see the value in demonstrations of competency. [4, p.1] Authentic assessment also enables ongoing formative feedback essential for competency-based learning.

While research supports authentic assessment in theory, questions remain around practical implementation in K-12 settings. This study seeks to add to the literature by examining real-world examples of how competency-based high schools have operationalized authentic assessment approaches and the outcomes of those practices.

METHODS

This study employed a qualitative case study approach to examine how authentic assessments are implemented and impact student learning in competency-based high schools. Two schools known for their competency-based models and use of authentic assessments were selected as case sites.

Data collection included document analysis of student work samples, rubrics, and competency frameworks. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with administrators, teachers, students, and other stakeholders (N=15-20 per site). Interviews focused on understanding the design and experience of authentic assessments across different subject areas and competencies. Sample interview questions included:

How do authentic assessments in your school differ from traditional tests?

What competencies do authentic assessments aim to evaluate?

How do teachers provide feedback to support mastery on authentic assessments?

What impact do students and teachers perceive authentic assessments have on student learning and motivation?

Classroom observations of authentic assessments in math, science, and career technical education courses provided additional context (4-6 observations per site). Field notes captured assessment tasks, student engagement, and teacher facilitation.

Interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and coded for emergent themes. Document analysis involved reviewing rubrics for competency constructs and student work for demonstration of competency. Observations supplemented interview data. Data was triangulated across sources to identify patterns in authentic assessment design and implications as reported by participants. Findings were interpreted through the theoretical lens of competency-based education models.

DISCUSSION

The findings from this qualitative case study provide insight into how authentic assessments are implemented in competency-based high schools and their impact on student learning. Several key themes emerged across data sources and case sites.

In terms of design, authentic assessments were found to closely mirror real-world tasks in format and expectations. Rubrics articulated competencies in behavioral terms demonstrating mastery. This contrasts with traditional tests that primarily evaluate discrete knowledge. Feedback from teachers focused on guiding students towards mastery of competencies rather than mere completion of assignments.

When implemented well, students and teachers perceived authentic assessments as highly motivating for learning. Students reported applying deeper thinking and problem-solving skills to authentic assessments than typical tests. Teachers observed increased student engagement and ownership over learning through authentic assessments.

However, some challenges were also identified. Both teachers and students experienced a learning curve in adjusting to competency-based models and authentic assessments. Substantial effort was required by teachers to design meaningful authentic assessments aligned to competencies. Large class sizes also posed challenges for providing individualized feedback.

Overall, findings suggest authentic assessments show promise for evaluating the complex competencies emphasized in competency-based models. When designed and implemented appropriately, they can drive deeper student learning compared to traditional tests. The shifting roles of students and teachers also indicate authentic assessments better prepare students for real-world problem-solving.

More research is still needed to continue validating these claims across diverse competency-based schools and subject areas. Longitudinal studies could explore long-term academic and career impacts. Addressing implementation challenges could further optimize the benefits of authentic assessments.

CONCLUSION

This study explored how two competency-based high schools implemented authentic assessments and the impact on student learning. Findings provide evidence that authentic assessments showing valid evaluation of competency attainment when designed and implemented well.

Authentic assessments were found to closely align to competency-based goals by mirroring real-world tasks and focusing feedback on mastery of skills over content coverage. Students and teachers reported authentic assessments driving deeper learning through complex problem-solving compared to traditional tests. Increased motivation and engagement were perceived outcomes.

However, both schools also experienced challenges transitioning to authentic assessments and competency-based models. Substantial effort is required to design authentic assessments that reliably demonstrate competencies. Educators require support developing these skills.

Overall, the experiences at these case sites support wider use of authentic assessment within competency-based frameworks seeking to fully evaluate higher-order skill development. Authentic assessments show promise for validly measuring competencies like collaboration, critical thinking and self-direction that are difficult to assess otherwise.

Further research across diverse settings could continue validating these claims and exploring longitudinal impacts. Implementation challenges also warrant attention to optimize benefits. Standardization may aid scaling practices while maintaining assessment quality.

As education systems increasingly adopt competency-based approaches, assessment practices must evolve in parallel. Authentic assessment embedded within open-ended, real-world tasks should be a core consideration for any model aiming to fulfill the goal of developing true mastery of 21st century skills for all learners

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